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ANALYSIS OF AIR POLLUTANT LEVEL USING DATA MINING TECHNIQUES IN CHENNAI CITY

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ABSTRACT

Air pollution refers to the release of harmful substances in the air that cause danger to human beings. Air pollution is becoming worse when compared to the past years due to many issues like Vehicle exhaust fumes, Fossil Fuel-Based power plants, exhaust from industrial plants and factories, construction and agricultural activities, natural causes and household activities. In this paper, Thiyagaraya Nagar (T.Nagar), Anna Nagar, Adyar, Kilpauk and Nungambakkam have been selected for air pollution analysis in Chennai city and it explores Respirable Suspended Particular Matter (RSPM), Sulphur diOxide (SO₂) and Nitrogen diOxide (NO₂) pollutant levels and compare these pollution levels in Chennai city. As per the National ambient air quality monitoring standards, the RSPM /PM₁₀, SO₂ and NO₂ levels are 60, 50 and 40 respectively. India stands in third place in the worst air quality ranking in world air quality standards, so it is more important to analyze the pollutant level in developing cities like Chennai. To attain these objectives, concepts of Data mining is used. It helps the Government to take initiatives in making policies and control air pollution.

Keywords: Airpollution, Data mining, Chennai city, Pollutant, RSPM, SO₂, NO₂

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is one of the major environmental problems especially in Chennai because of the growth of urbanization, industrialization, and the growth of the population. According to the survey of the global study, India stands in 58th rank in the emission of nitrogen dioxide due to vehicular emission and 4 million children were admitted to the hospital for asthma due to vehicular pollution [1].

Data mining is playing an important role in air pollution. The main aim of Data mining is used to extract useful patterns from a large set of databases. In this paper, Respirable Suspended Particular Matter (RSPM), Sulphur diOxide (SO₂) and Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) monthly pollutant levels are collected from the certain cities like Thiyagaraya Nagar (T.Nagar), Anna Nagar, Adyar, Kilpauk and Nungambakkam in Chennai. The data has been collected from the Tamil Nadu Pollution Control Board (<https://www.tnpcb.gov.in/>) website [2]. The pollutant components emission level for the year 2018 is considered for this analysis.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Ioannis N. Athanasiadis and Pericles A. Mitkas [3] have explained an intelligent environmental monitoring system, that uses software agents to analyze the air pollution from different sensors and used Data mining to add extra intelligence into the system and finally give an alarm when the pollution level exceeds the limit level to appropriate users. The C4.5 algorithm is used for validating incoming measurements, estimating the erroneous ones and the system was implemented using WEKA, JADE and protege 2000 OntologyEditor.

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Sabri Ghazi, Julie Dugdale, and Tarek Khadir [4] have described the human decision in the impacts of air pollution. Most of the paper describes the ecological and social parameters, but it introduces the human decision making. It used the two-stage air pollution modeling method: a GPD dispersion model and an ANN forecasting model. A cooperation strategy is also adopted in managing Air quality. The reward/penalty strategies also are used for effective air quality analysis. The main aim of the paper is the software agents are playing N Prisoner Dilemma game in which they have two decisions either to increase or decrease the emission. It also gives a brief explanation of the cooperation strategies.

Mihaela Oprea, Mădălina Cărbureanu, Elia Georgiana Dragomir [5] have described the collaborative intelligence in agents and it uses the C45 algorithm to extract the patterns from the large datasets. It has been implemented in Zeus and See5 Data mining. The AirQMAS system (Collaborative Multi-Agent System for Air Quality Analysis) will separate the air quality levels into strong pollutants and weak pollutants and send reports to the supervisor agent. It provides the air quality index and general report. The air pollutants that were analyzed are CO, SO₂, PM₁₀, H₂S, NO, NO₂, O₃ from 6 stations and it also uses the meteorological stations

Sabri Ghazi, Julie Dugdale, and Tarek Khadir [6] have described the multi-agent-based simulation approach and it was integrated with dispersion and prediction models to simulate the air pollution crisis. Including uncontrolled sources of pollutants is a key element for making the simulation more realistic. The simulation used PM₁₀, NO_x and SO_x data collected hourly from the city of Annaba and it also included climatic parameters like wind speed, humidity, and temperature. It also uses Cooperation strategies to reduce the effect of pollutant concentration.

Elia Georgiana Dragomir. Mihaela Oprea [7] have developed a Multi-agent system for monitoring urban air pollution due to power plants operating in the Ploiesti town area. It uses Artificial intelligence and Distributed simulation. Based on the real-time values, the air quality index is calculated. The main air pollutants like Carbon Monoxide, Nitrogen Monoxide, Nitrogen diOxide, Sulpher diOxide and particulate Matter are collected in three key places in Ploiesti city. This is mainly used for the deciding factors when the pollution level increases. It has been implemented in Zeus.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

As mentioned in the Literature review Data mining is used to discover patterns from the large dataset and helps in the process of decision making. In the proposed framework, a Filtered Classifier is used for validating the predicted values and find out the erroneous data and Simple-K Means Clustering is used to detect patterns from the datasets and used for decision making. The Proposed framework for the Data mining process is shown in Figure 1.

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Figure 1: Proposed framework using data mining

A. Preprocessor

Data preprocessing is a data mining technique that is used to transform the raw data into a useful and efficient format [8]. Data cleaning and transformation are methods used to remove outliers and standardize the data so that they take a form that can be easily used to create a model. The database sometimes contains unwanted data, and it leads to wrong analysis, so it is used to remove the unwanted data. And it is important to add the missing values. In the preprocessor, all the data will be preprocessed and fill the missing values by taking the mean, mode or median [9].

B. Validation

After the Preprocessor step has been completed, it enters into the Validation stage. Validation is performed by the Filtered Classifier. The structure of the filter is based exclusively on the training data and test instances will be processed by the filter without changing their structure [10]. In the validation stage, all the erroneous data will be removed and it is used to predict whether the predicted data is correctly classified or not. It is done by calculating the Accuracy.

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C. Cluster formation

Clustering is the task of dividing the population or data points into a number of groups such that data points in the same groups are more similar to other data points in the same group than those in other groups [11]. Clustering is the process of partitioning the data (or objects) into the same class. The data in one class is more similar to each other than to those in other clusters. The process of partitioning data objects into subclasses is called clusters.

D. Cluster detection

It is used to analyze the formulated cluster quality based on the quality parameters. Simple K- means clustering algorithm is used to find groups in the data, with the number of groups represented by the k variable. K means is an iterative clustering algorithm that aims to find local maxima in each iteration.

E. Visualization

Data Visualization is used to generate results. The result is based on the Clusters. The process of visualizing or displaying the data extracted in the form of different graphical or visual formats. Visualization is used to visualize the output in the 1D, 2D and 3D dimensional views. We can Select the different attributes from the list for the X and Y axis and the instances can be displayed as dots with a different color. Mining operations and mainly due to vehicular emission which has been shown in Figure2.

Figure 2: Air pollution in Chennai city

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Comparison results of RSPM, SO₂ and NO₂ in the following five areas like Kilpauk, T.Nagar, Nungambakkam, Anna Nagar and Adyar in Chennai city has been displayed in Figure 3, Figure 4 and Figure 5 respectively.

0-50 µg/m³ = GOOD 51-75 µg/m³ = MODERATE
76-90 µg/m³ = UNHEALTHY ABOVE 90 µg/m³ = VERYUNHEALTHY

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Figure 3: RSPM Comparision levels in Kilpauk, T.Nagar, Nungambakkam, Anna Nagar and Adyar areas in Chennai city

0-5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ =GOOD 6-9 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ = MODERATE
 10-12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ = UNHEALTHY ABOVE 12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ =VERYUNHEALTHY

Figure 4: SO₂ Comparision levels in Kilpauk, T.Nagar, Nungambakkam, Anna Nagar and Adyar areas in Chennai city

0-11 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ =GOOD 12-17 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ = MODERATE
 18-21 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ = UNHEALTHY ABOVE 21 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ =VERYUNHEALTHY

Figure 5: NO₂ Comparison levels in Kilpauk, T.Nagar, Nungambakkam, Anna Nagar and Adyar areas in Chennai city

1. Air pollution in Anna Nagar

Anna Nagar is one of the important areas in Chennai city. It is the major residential area for several lawyers, doctors, and politicians. It is the first polluted area because of several established schools colleges and shopping areas. It has many important locations such as AnnaArch, Chinthamani, Blue star, Padi grade separator and Anna Nagar railway station [12]. It is the main way to CMBT. Anna Nagar has a major pollutant of PM₁₀ and NO₂. The release of PM₁₀ is more during October, due to the construction of the subway between Anna Nagar East and Anna Tower Station. It is the first major polluted area among the five areas in Chennai, because of many commercial buildings, food manufacturing sectors especially due to the emission of smoke from cars.

2. Air pollution in Nungambakkam

Nungambakkam is the heart of Chennai because it has several shopping malls, tourist spots, star hotels, restaurants and cultural centers [13]. According to the observation, Nungambakkam is the second more polluted area because it has a higher concentration of PM₁₀ and NO₂. PM₁₀ is more polluted during June and July due to the construction of Foot overbridge in Nelson manikam road. It has many welding stations, manufacturing factories are the major reason for the release of NO₂ and it has many damaged roads which make to travel uneasy for people. And it is more polluted because of vehicular emissions. If the pollutant becomes high it results in worsened cough and wheezing and leads to many health effects like asthma and bronchitis.

3. Air pollution in Kilpauk

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Kilpauk is one of the most traffic areas in Chennai. It has major pollutants of SO₂ because of the burning of fossil fuels such as natural gases, coal, and oil. Many Industries are also the reason for the pollutant of SO₂. It is the fourth major polluted area. The major reason for the pollutant is due to the construction of metro rail and busy transportation. And mainly crowds will be all over in Kilpauk because of the Kilpauk Medical Hospital for their illness. It has the vision to offer the best in patient care and equipped with technologically advanced healthcare facilities. Kilpauk placed in the Poonamalle high road, so it is the main way to Chennai Mofussil Bus Terminus (CMBT). Taking a strict view of thermal power station's failure to meet emission standards, the Central Pollution Control Board_(CPCB) has issued warnings to 14 plants across six states of the country due to the emission of SO₂ [14].

4. Air pollution in Adyar

Adyar is the residential area located near the southern banks of Adyar river. It is less polluted compared to other cities but NO₂ emission is more because of the emission of vehicles especially the car. Sometimes the emission of NO₂ enters into the indoor which causes more adverse effects than outdoor pollution. As per the observation, every day 200 tons of waste are dumped into the city. Adyar rivers will be more polluted because of dumps and more pollutants released in the river. Cleaning has to be done in the respective region, if not more health impacts will be spread. When NO₂ and SO₂ released into the atmosphere, When it rains, the water droplets combine with these gases and fall into the ground in the form of acid rain.

5. Air pollution in T.Nagar

T.Nagar is known to be “Queen of textiles” .It has been more polluted because of many commercial buildings, textiles showrooms. Millions of people are wandering on their needs especially on the festive seasons. Lakhs of vehicular pollution also be the major reason for pollution. The above studies found that it has been more polluted during the festival seasons and especially in the month of December. The Burning of firecrackers leads to more pollutants such as particulate matter (PM₁₀). And the second-highest polluted season is in the month of June and July, mainly due to Aadi offers. And the third highest month is January because of the festival and long holidays.

CONCLUSION

Due to the rapid urbanization and industrialization, it makes more pollutants in Chennai particularly in Nungambakkam, Anna Nagar, and T.nagar because of more pollutants of RSPM and NO₂. If it increases more, it causes more dangers to human beings. So the analysis can help the Government to take initiatives to reduce the pollutant level and take measures to keep it under control, From the observation, it is found that Anna Nagar is more polluted when compared to other cities.

FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

This study is further extended in building a Data mining model using the agent paradigm. This work is also extended to other cities in Chennai, so we can discover alternative ways for a cleaner and greener environment.

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